

Original Software Publication

An open-source reference framework for the implementation of type 3 Asset Administration Shells

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ABSTRACT

Seamlessly integrating assets into distributed digital ecosystems based on Industry 4.0/5.0 demands measurable impact: lower engineering cost, interoperability and adaptability. SMIA (Self-configurable Manufacturing Industrial Agents) addresses this as a reference framework for implementing autonomous digital counterparts of assets, unifying industrial and software standards. Its dual-layer architecture combines machine-interpretable semantic modeling with distributed functional software, enhancing interoperability, flexibility, and autonomy. SMIA represents assets by executing domain-specific tasks and performing peer-to-peer communication through standardized interfaces. Following open scientific software principles, it integrates mature technologies and provides reproducible deployment artifacts (e.g., Docker), ensuring traceability and extensibility while reducing engineering effort and technological fragmentation.

Code metadata

Current code version	0.3.1
Permanent link to code/repository	https://github.com/SoftwareImpacts/SIMPAC-2025-327
Permanent link to Reproducible Capsule	https://pypi.org/project/smia/
License	GNU General Public License v3.0
Code versioning system used	Git
Programming language	Python 3.10+
Dependencies	spade, basyx-python-sdk, owlready2
Documentation location	https://smia.readthedocs.io/en/latest/
Installation instructions	https://smia.readthedocs.io/en/latest/smia_user_guide/installation_guide.html
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1. Introduction

The evolution of the Industry 4.0 paradigm and its transition to more human-centric paradigms such as Industry 5.0 reinforces the demand for connected, flexible, distributed and collaborative manufacturing systems. In this context, digital infrastructures must go beyond device connectivity and enable the integration of heterogeneous assets (physical or logical), with varying degrees of autonomy [1]. Unlike

passive representations, these components should be aligned with the Digital Twin (DT) concept in its operational sense: active digital counterparts that interact with physical assets, execute domain-specific skills, and autonomously interact within the distributed system.

To address these needs, several standardization efforts have emerged to provide common frameworks for interoperability and functional abstraction. The Asset Administration Shell (AAS) [2] standard stands out for defining structured digital representations of assets, with the

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evolutionary goal of achieving AAS Type 3, which enables peer-to-peer interactions between assets, realizing the vision of autonomous DTs. In parallel, the Capability-Skill-Service (CSS) model [3] specifies how to describe what and how an asset can do, while the Web Ontology Language (OWL) [4] offers a semantic foundation to formalize such descriptions, and the FIPA Agent Communication Language (ACL) [5] provides an interaction protocol among distributed agents. Although these initiatives offer a solid conceptual basis, they still lack a reproducible method to transform models into operational software components that integrate seamlessly into industrial processes.

Bridging this gap requires enabling technologies that can implement and extend these standards into practice. Ontologies support the enrichment of AAS with machine-interpretable semantics; industrial agents provide the software paradigm for distributed execution and coordination, acting as the operational layer that brings models into action. Based on these approaches several mature tools have emerged, such as Eclipse BaSyx [6] for AAS parsing and management, OWLReady2 [7] for ontology handling, and SPADE [8] for the development of distributed agents. However, they are often used in isolation, leaving open the challenge of integrating them into a unified solution that consistently connects modeling, standardization, and execution.

The Self-configurable Manufacturing Industrial Agents (SMIA) approach was presented in a previous work of authors to address this gap, from a conceptual point [9]. This paper details the software proposal underlying that work, the so-called SMIA software, a dual-layer reference framework that operationalizes existing standards for implementing autonomous digital counterparts of industrial assets. Architecturally, it combines standardized, machine-interpretable semantic modeling with distributed functional software, enabling it to act as a normalized AAS Type 3 component for any asset type, capable of peer-to-peer interactions. Built on Open Source Scientific Software Engineering principles and leveraging mature tools such as Eclipse BaSyx, OWLReady2, and SPADE, SMIA ensures replicability, extensibility, and alignment with current industrial practices.

The remainder of this article details the architecture and functionalities of the software, analyzes its performance as a result of an empirical validation, discusses its impact on current industrial context, and outlines future directions for development and potential improvements.

2. Software description

SMIA software aims to support the transition from Industry 4.0 to the digitization of manufacturing assets through a standards-based approach. This paradigm requires distributed social architectures that effectively integrate both physical and logical assets to create flexible manufacturing environments. To this end, SMIA complies with mature industrial standards and their specified requirements. The requirements were identified in [9], as well as, alternative approaches such as NOVAAS [10], FA³ST [11] or MAS4AI [12]. However, unless they address the use of similar paradigms, SMIA efficiently combines digital representations (AAS), semantics models for flexible production (CSS model with ontological implementation) and agent-based mechanisms (FIPA), placing at the proactive level where structured peer-to-peer messages can be exchanged and actions can be triggered autonomously. As a result, SMIA contributes to fulfilling a functional requirement in the context of interoperable asset integration, which could not be addressed without its architectural innovation, and without the additional autonomy and logic when extending or adapting each tool.

The development of the software was conducted by well-established principles of *Scientific Software Development Engineering*. The identified requirements have been considered, relying on documentation practices to record design decisions and rationales throughout the process, improving traceability and maintainability [13]. The development was guided by the specifications of relevant standards (AAS, CSS, OWL,

FIPA), ensuring that each software module is aligned with the corresponding part of the standard and that the overall solution faithfully implements the intended behavior, complying with standardization proposals.

Furthermore, the software is also based on *Open Source Software Engineering* and it was designed with a modular architecture, developing only the components that were strictly necessary. Indeed existing tools that could be integrated were leveraged, extending them when necessary to meet the required functionalities. Thus, existing solutions (AASX, BaSyx SDK, OWLReady2, SPADE) have been reused, reducing implementation effort, and ensuring alignment with the open principles. Since the software is developed in Python, the integration of existing solutions has been accomplished by leveraging the rich ecosystem of community-maintained packages, primarily distributed through the Python Package Index (PyPI) [14].

Following best practices for any kind of software, the implementation emphasizes version control, modular design, compliance with conventional commits specifications, avoidance of redundant code, and human-readable source code [15]. In the manufacturing domain, it is crucial that software solutions guarantee extensibility and adaptability across industrial contexts [16]. For this reason, SMIA is not conceived as a definitive complete solution, but rather offers well-defined extension mechanisms to adapt to different scenarios or requirements. These practices ensure that SMIA is reproducible, maintainable, and suitable for long-term adoption.

This section is divided into four subsections. The first two subsections present the conceptual and technological architectures, outlining how the proposal addresses the identified requirements and how the different tools and components are integrated to realize the design. The third subsection provides an overview of how the proposed software works. The last subsection details the developed toolset that supports this operation.

2.1. Software architecture

As presented in [9], the SMIA approach focuses on the automated generation of executable DTs capable of representing heterogeneous industrial assets. These DTs are endowed with proactive behavior, social interaction capabilities, and standardized semantic interoperability, enabling them to interact, coordinate, and actively participate in distributed manufacturing processes. The conceptual architecture was structured around three key axes: interoperability, flexibility, and autonomy [9]. In SMIA software, for each axis, related standardization proposals are analyzed, and existing open tools and resources are integrated if they are compatible with the overall approach. Fig. 1 presents the complete software architecture, illustrating the paradigms, tools and technologies integrated on the three main axes. The “SMIA extension” icon is added in those aspects where the SMIA software offers its own extension mechanism for adding new logic.

Interoperability is the central axis, which is addressed in the main industrial reference architectures, with the Reference Architecture Model Industrie 4.0 (RAMI 4.0) [17] emerging as one of the most mature and consolidated. The RAMI 4.0 model provides a layered framework that guides the integration of assets into smart factories. At its core lies the Asset Administration Shell (AAS), a standardized digital representation of industrial assets that enables unified access to their properties, status, and functionalities [2].

Such reference architectures define conceptual and normative frameworks for information models in the form of well-defined meta-models. According to the AAS standard, asset information must be organized into *Submodels*, each describing a specific aspect of the asset. Some of these aspects are common across different asset types and, following standardization principles, should be expressed through normalized templates to ensure reuse and seamless integration across multiple solutions. Some templates have been adapted for SMIA to describe common aspects such as the interface with the asset (Asset Interfaces Description

Fig. 1. SMIA software architecture with integrated paradigms and tools.

submodel [18]) or the identification of the software itself within industrial environments (Nameplate for Software in Manufacturing submodel [19]).

The implementation of these standardized and structured information models requires machine-readable formats and suitable development toolkits. The Industrial Digital Twin Association (IDTA) provides standardized specifications to create and manage the AAS [20]. The SMIA software integrates these specifications, specially the meta-model, where the general structure of the AAS is defined and implementations are provided in XML or JSON format [21]. Besides, IDTA maintains a repository of submodel templates for common aspects of the assets. Regarding the development toolkit, SMIA integrates the BaSyx Python SDK [6], which allows parsing, validating and transforming AAS models into programming objects according to the specification. SMIA software extends the Basyx SDK package classes with key methods for validating CSS-enriched AAS models and managing semantically identified elements. Domain-specific methods are also added through a non-invasive mechanism that extends classes by linking attributes, preserving the integrity of the package's source code.

Another key axis is flexibility, understood as adaptation to dynamic contexts through modular and interpretable descriptions of the functionalities of the assets (what they can do) and their implementations (how they do it). The CSS model stands out as an industrial initiative that seeks the implementation of well-defined concepts in machine readable formats. This model modularizes production resources and requirements, and abstracts them into three functional levels: capabilities (functional description), skills (implementation), and services (commercial exposure) [3]. The SMIA approach proposes linking the CSS model with the AAS through ontological semantic identification, enabling their decoupling while maintaining interoperability. Ontologies provide a rich, machine-readable, and extensible description of the CSS model, allowing capabilities and skills to be represented in a reusable and software-interpretable manner. Thus, the SMIA incorporates the CSS model using OWL [4], the most established ontology language and a standard promoted by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) [22]. To enable its seamless integration with the rest of the system, the OWLReady2 [7] Python library is employed, which offers ontology-oriented programming features for the manipulation and management of OWL ontologies. SMIA software has also leveraged OWLReady2 to add methods to ontological classes, which are essential for managing

the CSS model (e.g., checking the required properties of ontological concepts).

In addition to standardized information models, the software must incorporate a degree of autonomy, enabling it to act and coordinate without external supervision. Among the available paradigms, the most suitable is Multi-Agent Systems (MAS), which provide a robust framework for distributed, autonomous, and cooperative behaviors. To ensure efficient operation, these behaviors must be explicitly defined. Accordingly, SMIA agents are designed following a finite state machine (FSM) approach, which specifies the logic of agents throughout their operational lifecycle, in terms of states (related behaviors) and the transitions between these states (triggered by events or conditions). SMIA software employs SPADE [8] as its agent-based development framework, benefiting from its modular, asynchronous, and extensible architecture. Its maturity, active maintenance, and compliance with open standards make SPADE particularly suitable for interoperable industrial applications [23]. The use of SPADE to develop an FSM-based agent simplifies and facilitates the identification of the software's operational stages, so that specific behaviors are developed and added to provide the necessary autonomy for each agent state.

Distributed environments for flexible manufacturing also require peer-to-peer interactions between components, often referred to as I4.0 Languages. Within the industrial agent paradigm, this challenge has been addressed by the Foundation for Intelligent Physical Agents (FIPA), which proposed a standardized communication language to ensure interoperability and support the requirements of social interactions, proposed as FIPA-ACL [5]. Given its compatibility with SPADE, FIPA-ACL has been adopted as the I4.0 communication language, providing agents with embedded social capabilities.

Additionally, since SMIA software seeks to represent manufacturing assets, seamless integration with physical assets is another critical aspect. For this reason, the SMIA software is IEEE 2660.1:2020-compliant, a standard that defines how software agents integrate with low-level automation functions responsible for asset control [24]. This guides SMIA to define a reusable agent template regardless of the asset interface.

As previously outlined, SMIA provides clear extension mechanisms to incorporate new logic in three key aspects to address novel scenarios. First, it offers templates for defining new connection classes, enabling the integration of assets with additional communication capabilities.

Moreover, since SPADE defines agent logic in terms of behaviors, SMIA enhances agent autonomy by allowing the specification of new cognitive or social functions as custom capabilities (*AgentCapabilities*). Finally, considering that the CSS model skills are accessed through executable implementations that could be part of the software itself (agent functionalities), the software allows new logic to be added by defining new agent services.

2.2. How SMIA works

Integrated paradigms and technologies allow some parts of the internal logic to be externalized. Even so, to achieve the goal of meeting all identified requirements, SMIA presents its own algorithms to increase the efficiency of the functioning of the software.

SMIA software offers structural scalability as it comprises a cornerstone capable of generating DTs from standardized models, i.e. CSS-enriched AAS models. This process is called self-configuration, described in [9]. Its algorithm is shown as pseudocode in Algorithm 1, and it constitutes the first step of the software's operational model. During this process, asset integration is also automated by extracting the necessary information about the interface from the standardized Asset Interfaces Description submodel [18]. Then, the software searches for CSS elements within the AAS model and validates that they are correctly linked semantically. If so, the corresponding ontological instances are created, thus building a functional structure aligned with the CSS model.

Algorithm 1 SMIA software algorithm for the self-configuration process

```

1: var aasModelFile = loadAASXFile()
2: loadCSSOntologyFromOWL() → OWLReady2
3: var aasModelObject = parseAASModel(aasModelFile) → Basyx SDK

4: for each defined asset interface do
5:   var interfaceSubmodelElement = getFromSubmodel(assetInterfacesDescription-Submodel, assetInterface)
6:   var interfaceClass = createAssetConnectionClass(interfaceSubmodelElement)
7: end for

8: for each AAS element semantically linked to CSS do
9:   var result = validateAgainstCSSOntology(aasElement, ontologyIRI)
10:  if result == true then
11:    var ontologyInstance = createOWLInstance(aasElement, ontologyIRI)
12:  end if
13: end for

14: for each AAS relationship semantically linked to CSS do
15:   var result = validateRelAgainstCSSOntology(aasRelElement, relOntologyIRI)
16:   if result == true then
17:     linkOWLInstances(aasElementFirst, aasElementScond, relOntologyIRI)
18:   end if
19: end for

```

After self-configuration, SMIA software offers operational behaviors for when the ACL-compliant communications need to be managed (see Algorithm 2). Some of the behaviors are dedicated to managing agent communications within the MAS, and others dedicated to executing specific tasks linked to the requested capabilities or services. The former remain active to continuously analyze incoming messages that comply with FIPA-ACL and, taking advantage of the fact that the language is semantically rich, verify whether they comply with certain defined patterns. If so, the latter behaviors are dynamically generated to handle and manage these specific requests. Furthermore, these behaviors are implemented through asynchronous and distributed logic based on FSM, which allows structuring its functions in a modular way.

Algorithm 2 SMIA software algorithm for external communications management

```

1: behaviour ACLCommunicationBehaviour
2: loop analyze incoming ACL messages
3:   var newMessage = getReceivedACLMessage()
4:   switch new 14.0 message ontology → FIPA ontology attribute
5:     case css - request do:
6:       initialize instance handleCSSBehaviour(newMessage) → SPADE
7:     case aas - request do:
8:       initialize instance handleAASBehaviour(newMessage) → SPADE
9:   end loop
10: end behaviour

11: behaviour handleCSSBehaviour(aclMessage)
12: validateCSSInformation(aclMessage, cssOntology)
13: obtainAssetInformation(aclMessage, aasModel) → from AID submodel
14: var result = performCSSTask(aclMessage)
15: replyToACLSender(aclMessage, result)
16: end behaviour

17: behaviour handleAASBehaviour(aclMessage)
18: var result = performAASTask(aclMessage)
19: replyToACLSender(aclMessage, result)
20: end behaviour

```

2.3. How to deploy SMIA

Although SMIA is a complex software that integrates several standards, paradigms, and technologies, it has been designed to automate part of its operation, thus simplifying both deployment and usage. This section is divided into two parts: the first subsection describes the procedure to successfully deploy an SMIA instance, while the second provides the additional tools offered to ease specific tasks within the workflow.

2.3.1. SMIA deployment procedure

Fig. 2 illustrates the SMIA deployment process, which follows a DevOps-inspired approach and comprises three phases. Among them, the design and deployment phases are mandatory, while the set-up phase is only required when extending with new logic.

The design phase focuses on producing a valid CSS-enriched AAS model, which is a prerequisite for SMIA to configure itself. From the industrial profile perspective, this involves identifying the asset to be represented, along with its functionalities (i.e., CSS-related concepts). The AAS model can then be defined using an AAS editor such as the one proposed by IDTA: the AASX Package Explorer [25]. Users can query the CSS ontology with an OWL editor like Protégé [26], retrieving the necessary semantic identifiers. The outcome is a valid CSS-enriched AAS model in AASX format, which enables encapsulating the model together with complementary files.

The set-up phase should be followed in cases where the SMIA base needs to be extended with new features. After identifying the needs, the associated new logic is programmed in Python. Depending on the type of extension, specific patterns must be followed (e.g., SMIA provides a class template for new asset interfaces). These extensions are integrated into the SMIA base through the *ExtensibleSMIAAgent* class, which exposes the necessary mechanisms for adding new features.

With all resources ready, the deployment phase can begin. First, the execution environment is selected, since the SMIA software supports multiple options: running as a Python program (PyPI package or CLI executable) or running as a Docker container. Two requirements must be guaranteed: the availability of the CSS-enriched AAS model, and access to an XMPP server, as SMIA relies on SPADE technology. If SMIA needs to interact with its associated asset, the defined interface must also be accessible. Once these conditions are met, an SMIA instance can be deployed using a single AASX file as input (containing the valid model).

Fig. 2. Graphical procedure for successful SMIA deployment.

Fig. 3. SMIA ecosystem with provided tools and resources.

2.3.2. SMIA additional supporting tools

To further simplify and facilitate the deployment and operation of SMIA, several supporting tools have been developed to assist users during different phases and tasks. Fig. 3 illustrates the SMIA ecosystem with all the provided tools and resources.

For the generation of valid CSS-enriched AAS models, two resources are provided. The AASX Package editor allows to design and develop AAS models in compliance with the specifications. Specifically, to achieve this kind of semantically rich models, SMIA software has added a plug-in to this tool that automatically generates a Submodel template with all CSS-related identifiers [27], allowing direct access to them and easing the AAS model development. Alternatively, as stated above, users can query the CSS model in ontology-specific editors. To this end, the adapted CSS ontology has been published through W3ID [28], allowing seamless integration into OWL-based tools such as Protégé.

To support interactions during the orchestration of manufacturing processes by the operator, a dedicated SMIA agent has been implemented (SMIA Operator) [29]. Since SMIA instances communicate through FIPA-ACL-compliant messages, which are semantically complex, this agent provides a web-based graphical user interface, acting as a control pane. It enables operators to automatically discover available SMIA instances and their corresponding CSS-enriched information, as well as to request the execution of specific capabilities and assign them to the appropriate agents. By separating the capability selection from the agent assignment, the interface guides the operator through

decision-making without requiring detailed technical knowledge of each asset.

Finally, to foster transparency and reproducibility, the source code of SMIA approach is available in a GitHub repository [30], accompanied by a technical documentation platform that helps with each aspect of the solution [31]. Ready-to-use deployment artifacts are also accessible on PyPI [32] and Docker Hub [33]. Additionally, supplementary visual resources are provided in the paper that introduces SMIA [9], offering further support for understanding its key aspects.

3. Performance evaluation

To evaluate the performance of SMIA, four different scenarios and experiments were designed, key metrics were obtained, and a comprehensive analysis was conducted. The first three experiments were structured and designed to obtain meaningful results, considering that this paper focuses on SMIA’s architectural innovation and its ability to parse and interpret semantically enriched AAS models, while preparing to become part of a MAS. Two aspects related to SMIA’s key processes were analyzed: the self-configuration process of DTs and their operational readiness in the MAS. Additionally, an exhaustive comparison with alternative solutions was also performed.

The test bench used was a DELL OptiPlex 7060 equipped with an Intel Core i5-8500 processor (6 cores) and 16 GB of DDR4 RAM, running Ubuntu 22.04.5 LTS on a VMware virtual machine with 4 cores

Fig. 4. Performance evaluation experiments over SMIA software: (a) scaling capacity during SMIA deployment, as a function of number of instances; (b) processing capacity of CSS-enriched AAS models, as a function of the number of submodels; (c) processing capacity of CSS-enriched AAS models, as a function of the number of ontological concepts.

and 12 GB of RAM. The SMIA source code was slightly modified by introducing timers at key execution points to enable precise performance tracking. Docker Compose was used to deploy the required agents in each experimental case. Raw execution data were collected in CSV files, subsequently aggregated using Microsoft Excel, and finally analyzed in R using RStudio. Each experiment consisted of 30 independent runs to ensure statistical significance.

The first scenario evaluates the scaling capacity during SMIA deployment, by increasing the number of instances (from 1 to 64). As depicted in Fig. 4a, $T_{selfconf}$ increases slightly from 2.22 s ($\sigma^2 \approx 6.7 \cdot 10^{-5}$) to 2.42 s ($\sigma^2 \approx 1.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$), while T_{ready} grows from 0.0050 s ($\sigma^2 \approx 6.8 \cdot 10^{-7}$) to 0.0130 s ($\sigma^2 \approx 1.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$). SMIA exhibits efficient scalability in both self-configuration and operational readiness, with the per-instance cost approximately halving as the number of instances doubles. A Kruskal–Wallis test confirms a significant effect of the number of instances on both metrics ($T_{selfconf}$: $\chi^2 = 1227.5$, T_{ready} : $\chi^2 = 829.4$, $df = 6$, $p < 0.001$). Dunn’s post-hoc tests with Bonferroni correction show non-significant differences for 1–4 instances and significant changes from 8 instances onward. Overall, the

results demonstrate stable performance and sustained efficiency even in large-scale deployments of up to 64 instances.

The second and third scenarios focus on SMIA capacity to process CSS-enriched AAS models. The second scenario evaluates performance as a function of the AAS size, by increasing the number of submodels (from 1 to 64). $T_{selfconf}$ rises from 1.08s ($\sigma^2 \approx 1.11 \cdot 10^{-4}$) to 2.29s ($\sigma^2 \approx 1.13 \cdot 10^{-6}$), following a non-linear trend (see Fig. 4.b): sharp increases between 1–4 submodels, moderate between 4–8, and near stable behavior between 8–64. Scalability is evidenced by the sharp decrease in the cost per submodel. A Kruskal–Wallis test confirms a significant effect of the number of submodels on $T_{selfconf}$ ($\chi^2 = 195.84$, $df = 6$, $p < 2.2 \cdot 10^{-16}$), while Dunn’s post-hoc tests with Bonferroni correction show significant differences in nearly all comparisons ($p_{adj} < 0.01$). By contrast, T_{ready} remains almost constant, between 0.0047 s and 0.0055 s ($\sigma^2 \approx 1 \cdot 10^{-6}$), with differences below internal variability. The Kruskal–Wallis test indicates no significant effect of number of submodels ($\chi^2 = 8.98$, $df = 6$, $p = 0.175$), demonstrating that operational readiness is achieved regardless of the number of submodels. The third scenario also evaluates SMIA capacity to process CSS-enriched AAS models, but in terms of the CSS complexity, by

Fig. 5. Comparison of SMIA with NOVAAS [10] and FA³ST [11].

increasing the number of ontological concepts semantically identified in the AAS model. As shown in Fig. 4.C, $T_{selfconf}$ increases from 1.16 s ($\sigma^2 \approx 1.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$) to 4.41 s ($\sigma^2 \approx 9.31 \cdot 10^{-7}$), following an approximately \log_2 growth pattern. Scalability is evidenced by a sharp reduction in the cost per concept, from 1.16 s to 0.069 s, indicating an increasing efficiency in larger ontologies. A Kruskal–Wallis test confirms a highly significant effect of the number of ontological concepts on $T_{selfconf}$ ($\chi^2 = 204.56$, $df = 6$, $p < 2.2 \cdot 10^{-16}$), while Dunn’s post-hoc test with Bonferroni correction shows significant differences for most level comparisons ($p_{adj} < 0.01$). On the contrary, T_{ready} remains nearly constant (from 0.00438 s to 0.00487 s, $\sigma^2 \approx 1 \cdot 10^{-6}$), with differences smaller than internal variability. The Kruskal–Wallis test indicates no significant effect of ontological complexity ($\chi^2 = 1.93$, $df = 6$, $p = 0.926$), demonstrating that operational readiness is independent of CSS complexity.

The last scenario compares SMIA with the alternative solutions NOVAAS [10] and FA³ST [11]. All solutions interpret and expose AAS models: NOVAAS and FA³ST via an HTTP-based interface, and SMIA via an I4.0 Language-based (FIPA-ACL) interface within a MAS. The comparison was conducted under identical conditions (synchronized start and simultaneous deployment) to assess AAS model analysis and exposure performance. T_{ready} , which includes $T_{selfconf}$, exhibits systematic and pronounced differences across platforms (see Fig. 5). Based on descriptive statistics, SMIA shows the highest mean values (≈ 11.1 – 12.5 s), followed by FA³ST (≈ 10.7 – 12.1 s), while NOVAAS consistently achieves the lowest times (≈ 8.4 – 9.5 s). Variance is higher in low-complexity scenarios (1–4 submodels), particularly for FA³ST and NOVAAS, and stabilizes with increasing complexity, converging to approximately 1.3–2.0 s for the higher levels (32–64 submodels). A Kruskal–Wallis test confirms a highly significant platform effect on T_{ready} ($\chi^2 = 397.13$, $df = 2$, $p < 2.2 \cdot 10^{-16}$). Dunn’s post-hoc tests with Bonferroni correction indicate statistically significant differences for all pairwise comparisons: FA³ST vs. NOVAAS ($p_{adj} = 2.42 \cdot 10^{-38}$), FA³ST vs. SMIA ($p_{adj} = 1.83 \cdot 10^{-10}$) and NOVAAS vs. SMIA ($p_{adj} = 7.94 \cdot 10^{-85}$).

4. Impacts

Although standards promise interoperability and reduced vendor dependency, actual implementations are scarce, partly due to the technical and conceptual complexity. SMIA provides practical and seamless integration of assets into distributed digital ecosystems based on consolidated standards. The proposed software has been recently conceptualized and is constantly evolving, with new features and bug fixes as it is validated in increasingly complex scenarios. The software has been

qualitatively validated in [9], under simulated conditions, reducing technical uncertainty, in a use case focused on assessing the viability of the self-configuration process. In this context, SMIA demonstrated its ability to generate industrial agents representing physical assets (mobile robots) and humans, being able to interpret semantically enriched standardized models and manage ontological semantics. The experiments conducted exemplified a Human-in-the-mesh paradigm, where the human acted as an active participant in the digital manufacturing ecosystem. However, this validation is framed within a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) level 3–4, so future use cases will be designed for TRL 5–6 (network failures, more complex heterogeneous assets, etc.).

The quantitative evaluation conducted in this paper outlines that the SMIA software exhibits a coherent and stable performance across several scenarios. The scaling experiment confirms that the number of instances has a statistically significant impact on performance, with the cost per instance decreasing as the system scales. This evidences efficient scalability, maintaining both self-configuration and operational readiness times within narrow and predictable limits even at higher deployment levels. Regarding the standardized model from which SMIA configures itself, the analysis reveals that the number of submodels has a strong and significant influence on self-configuration time, but does not have a statistically significant impact on the time required to reach operational readiness. A similar effect is observed in the CSS complexity experiment: while self-configuration time increases with the number of ontological concepts, the cost per concept decreases as ontological size grows, further confirming SMIA’s high scalability when processing increasingly complex CSS structures. Finally, the benchmarking results present higher absolute times than those obtained in the previous experiments, which can be attributed to the need to enforce identical execution conditions across all compared platforms to ensure a fair and consistent analysis. However, the comparison presents meaningful results, as the evaluated solutions are ranked based on their architectural complexity and functional scope: NOVAAS relies on external tools, such as Node-RED, to expose AAS information; FA³ST configures its own access endpoints; and SMIA performs an augmented semantic analysis of the AAS model while generating an intelligent agent to be included in a distributed MAS, being the only one to achieve an AAS Type 3. These additional features explain the observed performance differences and the trade-off between operational readiness and functional richness.

The software is currently being used and improved on two research projects. In the project with the funding reference KK-2025/00035 it is the cornerstone of a multi-agent system composed of different types of digitized assets, with a particular focus on the human Digital Twin. SMIA will be used to model and generate DT for humans, as well as an enabling tool to explore LLMs for human–machine interaction. The goal is to use this digitization process on different assets to generate

manufacturing management platforms composed of SMIA instances. Outside the manufacturing domain, the software will be used within the European project with the funding reference POCTEFA 2021–2027 EFA030/01 AgriPower. In this project, SMIA will enable to explore how to apply the AAS concept in a non-industrial context, analyzing whether it can meet the information needs of the different subsystems that make up an agrivoltaics system, considering that this information comes from its corresponding monitoring. SMIA will also be used as a mechanism for sharing this information between different modules to make the most appropriate decisions.

A key contribution lies in extending existing industrial reference architectures to align with Industry 4.0 paradigms. The proposal introduces a lightweight, open-source reference framework that minimizes configuration efforts and supports progressive adoption, which is critical in current environments. This approach reduces technological uncertainty and provides a structured pathway toward higher levels of digital maturity. Although several mature tools are integrated, they are systematically extended and adapted to support the specific requirements of interoperable asset integration. This interoperability level could not be achieved without the additional autonomy and architectural innovations introduced by the proposed framework. As a result, the proposal directly addresses the prevalent industrial scenario, where most implementations remain constrained to limited pilot initiatives.

The proposed software advances interoperability by formalizing asset representation through AAS and CSS information models, enabling both technical and semantic integration across heterogeneous assets. By providing extension mechanisms, the proposed software further enhances adaptability to new scenarios, balancing compliance with standards and practical flexibility. On the operational level, the solution enables capability- and skill-based work order allocation, improving resource utilization, responsiveness, and modularization, while interacting through semantically rich peer-to-peer languages. These features collectively enhance productivity and reduce the cost of implementing flexibility, particularly in highly automated and customized manufacturing contexts. In essence, the framework achieves the vision of the autonomous DT by leveraging the AAS Type 3. The software also generates organizational and socio-economic benefits by fostering knowledge transfer and enabling the emergence of hybrid professional profiles. Its lightweight and modular design lowers barriers to adoption and facilitates scalable, cost-effective deployment, which is particularly relevant for SMEs constrained by outdated infrastructures and limited expertise.

5. Limitations and potential improvements

Although SMIA software represents a comprehensive approach that aligns with consolidated standards and integrates multiple paradigms and technologies, it cannot yet be considered a definitive solution. Several challenges remain that must be addressed to overcome current limitations and to strengthen its applicability in real industrial contexts.

The current evaluation of the proposed software was conducted under simulated conditions with a limited number of agents and context-sensitive services. Consequently, aspects critical for industrial deployment, such as scalability, heterogeneous asset behavior, and real-time communication constraints, were not fully addressed. These limitations restrict the extrapolation of results to large-scale industrial environments, where variability, unpredictability, and latency issues are critical.

Future improvements will address these limitations by extending the solution's connectivity and representational capabilities. A primary focus will be on incorporating industrial communication protocols that currently are not supported, such as OPC UA, which are fundamental for integration with existing infrastructures. This can be achieved thanks to packages from the broad Python community such as "opcua-asyncio", essential for this software as it relies on the SPADE's asynchronous execution. In parallel, the architecture will be expanded

to include purely digital assets, such as cognitive services or AI-based agents, which require semantic descriptions to interoperate effectively. This evolution will also enable automated execution of flexible production plans considering also the human as production asset. As for asset descriptions, other standard formats can be adapted and linked to CSS-enriched AAS models, leveraging existing mappings between AAS and other interoperability initiatives, such as OPC UA or AutomationML information models [34–36]. In this way, SMIA shows potential to serve as a pathway to open, interoperable, and people-centered industrial systems.

From an implementation standpoint, the solution already supports modular extension through well-defined own mechanisms. This provides a robust foundation for future scalability and adaptability. Moreover, the availability of the solution as Docker containers opens opportunities for streamlined deployment and lifecycle management using container orchestration platforms such as Kubernetes. However, several technical limitations related to deployment remain. SPADE integration results in a reliance on an XMPP server, which limits the software applicability. Containerization technologies (e.g., Docker and Kubernetes) provide a solution by offering the possibility of deploying an encapsulated XMPP server. Another possibility is to use other message transfer protocols by modifying the SPADE communication module, which has already been addressed with JADE technology [37]. These advances will contribute not only to technical robustness but also to bridging the gap between standardization and its practical adoption.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ekaitz Hurtado: Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Isabel Sarachaga:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Aintzane Armentia:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Oskar Casquero:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

The content of this manuscript was entirely conceived and written by the authors. ChatGPT was used only to enhance the previously developed text in terms of grammar and style, without contributing to the intellectual content. The authors reviewed the final version after using this tool and take full responsibility for the published work.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The source code of SMIA software is available at the following GitHub repository: <https://github.com/ekhurtado/SMIA> (accessed on 22 October 2025). An associated technical documentation platform is also available at <https://smia.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> (accessed on 22 October 2025). Regarding the ontology proposal of the CSS model, it is available as a W3ID identifier at <https://w3id.org/upv-ehu/gcis/css-smia/> (accessed on 22 October 2025). Regarding the SMIA performance evaluation, a dataset is available at [38] with raw data in CSV files, pre-processed analytical files, analytical R commands, reproduction scripts, and used AASX files.

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